

Study of Complications during Pseudo Exfoliation Cataract Surgery in Maharashtra Rural Population

Surajkumar Shobhalal Kuril¹, Dinesh Ganpat Patil², Chetan Surajkumar Kuril³

¹Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Govt Medical College Nandurbar Maharashtra

²Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Govt Medical College Nandurbar Maharashtra

³Junior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Govt Medical College Nandurbar Maharashtra

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Surajkumar Kuril

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Pseudo exfoliation (PEX) is an age-related systemic disorder in which fibrillar extracellular material is synthesized and deposited in the anterior segment of the eye. Hence, cataract surgery in PEX poses a challenge to ophthalmic surgeons.

Method: 50 patients above fifty years of age with PEX were studied; planned manual small incision cataract surgery with rigid posterior chamber intraocular lens implantation under peribulbar anesthesia was carried out.

Results: 22 (44%) patients had intraoperative complications. The major postoperative complications were 16 (32%) corneal oedema with sk's, 15 (30%) had severe AC reactions, and 7 (14%) Iris pigment dispersion.

Conclusion: It is concluded that proper preoperative evaluation and modification of surgical technique are essential to manage intraoperative complications and successful cataract surgery with PEX.

Keywords: Slit lamp examination, pseudo exfoliation, visual acuity, glaucoma, intraocular pressure, Maharashtra.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Pseudo exfoliation is an age-related systemic disorder in which fibrillar extracellular material is synthesized and deposited throughout the anterior segment of the eye [1]. Pseudo exfoliation was first described by Lindberg in 1917, and the full description of pseudo exfoliation was explained by Alfred Vogt, a Swiss ophthalmologist, in 1925 [2]. It is most prevalent in age between 60 and 70 years. Pseudo exfoliation (PEX) results in more complications during cataract surgery. PEX is frequently associated with open-angle glaucoma and poor pupillary dilatation [3].

The greater risk of complications during cataract surgery such as posterior capsular rupture, zonular dialysis, and hyphema. The immediate postoperative period is also fraught with complications, mainly corneal epithelial and stromal edema.

Increased intraocular pressure, secondary glaucoma, and decentration of intraocular lens (IOL) are other complications. Late postoperative complications mainly included progressive weakness of the zonules, decentration and dislocation of IOL and decomposition of the corneal endothelium [4]. Hence, an attempt is made to evaluate the preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative complications.

Material and Method

50 elderly patients aged between 50-90 regularly visited the ophthalmology department, Government Medical College Nandurbar Maharashtra-425412, were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients above 50 years, diagnosed as cataracts with pseudo exfoliation on the basis of slit lamp examination. The patient gave consent in writing for studies and was selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients below fifty years, patients with traumatic cataracts, congenial cataracts, patients with raised intraocular pressure (> 20 mm of Hg), patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, and severe cardio-vascular diseases were excluded from the study.

Method: Every patient underwent a detailed medical and ocular history. Visual acuity, pupillary dilatation funduscopy, lacrimal sac syringing, and intraocular pressure were studied. A slit lamp examination was done to note the status of the cornea, anterior chamber depth and pigment dispersion, pseudo exfoliation material over the anterior lens capsule and pupillary border, and phacodonesis. Nuclear sclerosis grading and cataract grading were

based on the lens opacity classification system (LOCS-III). Intraocular lens power calculation was done using the SRK-T formula.

All the patients were planned for manual small incision cataract surgery with rigid posterior chamber intraocular lens implantation under peribulbar anesthesia. (1) Usage of intraoperative adrenaline (Epitrate), (2) Mechanical stretching of the pupil, (3) Sphincterotomy, (4) type of capsulotomy, and (5) Use of CTR/any other untoward event.

Adequate peribulbar block was given, the size of the scleral tunnel corresponding to nuclear sclerosis was fashioned liberal use of viscoelastic protecting the corneal endothelium, wherever required,

epitrate was used, and sphincterotomy was done, especially in small pupils or nuclear sclerosis > grade 4. A thorough cortical wash was given, and postoperative topical and systemic steroids or antiglucoma drugs were given appropriately. Postoperative complications were recorded, and patients were followed up on 1st, 7th, 40th day.

The duration of the study was February 2024 to July 2024.

Statistical analysis: Distribution of age of patients preoperative intra-operative, postoperative complications were classified with percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of male and female was 2:1.

Figure 1 Slit lamp photograph showing signs of cataract and pseudoexfoliation.

Figure 2 Intraoperative photograph showing capsule retractors stenting the capsular bag during phacoemulsification.

Figure 3 Slit lamp photograph showing anterior capsule opacification and phimosis after cataract surgery with in-the-bag IOL implantation.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Distribution of age in patients: 35 (70%) were aged between 50-69, 14 (28%) were aged between 70-89, 1 (2%) was above 90 years.

Table 2:

Pre-operative feature: 13 (26%) had a small pupil (< 7mm), 1 (2%) had posterior synechie.

Table 3: Study of intra-operative complications: 1 (2%) zonular dialysis, 4 (8%) difficulty in nucleus

delivery, 4 (8%) sphincterotmy, 3 (6%) PC rent, 2 (4%) iridodialysis, 2 (4%) vitreous loss, 1 (2%) hyphaema, and 5 (10%) residual matter.

Table 4:

Post-operative complications 1 (2%) posterior synechiae, 7 (14%) iris pigment dispersion, 16 (32%) corneal oedema SKS, 15 (30%) severe AC reaction, 3 (6%) postoperative rise of IOP, 4 (8%) irregular pupil, 3 (6%) exudative membrane, 1 (2%) decentred IOL.

Table 1: Distribution of age in pseudo exfoliation patients (Total No. of patients: 50)

Age in years	No of patients	Percentage (%)
50-69	35	70
70-89	14	28
>90	1	2
Total	50	100

Figure 4: Distribution of age in pseudo exfoliation patients

Table 2: Pre-operative features in patients with pseudo exfoliation patients

Sl. No	Pre-operative complications	No of patients	Percentage (%)
1	Small pupil (< 7mm)	13	26
2	Posterior synechie	1	2

Figure 5: Pre-operative features in patients with pseudo exfoliation patients

Table 3: Study of Intra-operative complications in patients with exfoliation

Sl. No	Intra operative complications	No of patients	Percentage (%)
1	Zonal Dialysis	1	2
2	Difficulty in Nucleus delivery	4	8
3	Sphincterotomy	4	8
4	PC rent	3	6
5	Iridodialysis	2	4
6	Vitreous loss	2	4
7	Hyphaema	1	2
8	Residual cortical matter	5	10
	Total	22	44

Figure 6: Study of Intra-operative complications in patients with exfoliation

Table 4: Study of Post-operative complications in patients with pseudo exfoliation

Sl. No	Post-operative complications	No of patients (50)	Percentage (%)
1	Posterior synechiae	1	2
2	Iris pigment dispersion	7	14
3	Corneal oedema with SKS	16	32
4	Severe AC reaction	15	30
5	Post-operative rise of IOP	3	6
6	Irregular pupil due to sphincteromy	4	8
7	Exudative membrane	3	6
8	Decentred IOL	1	2
	Total	50	100

Figure 7: Study of Post-operative complications in patients with pseudo exfoliation

Discussion

Present study of complications during pseudo exfoliation cataract surgery in Maharashtra population. The pre-operative features in patients with PEX were 13 (26%) had a small pupil (<7 mm) and 1 (2%) had posterior synechie (Table 2). Intraoperative operative complication was 4 (8%) difficulty in nucleus delivery, 4 (8%) sphincterotomy, and 5 (10%) residual cortical matter. The total number of patients was 22 (44%) (Table 3). The major postoperative complications were 16 (32%) corneal oedema with SKS, 15 (30%) had severe AC reaction, and 7 (14%) had Iris pigment dispersion (Table 4) (Figure 1, 2 and 3). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

The association between PEX and the development of cataract is biologically plausible. Electron microscopic examination of the iris vasculature in eyes with PEX revealed multiple abnormalities, including deposits of pseudo exfoliation material tying adjacent to the vascular endothelial wall, thin vessel basement membrane sometimes even interrupted, extreme reduction of vessel lamina through increased volume of the endothelial cells, and fen-

estration of the vascular endothelial wall [8]. It is also observed that the rate of aqueous flow through the anterior chamber was lower in eyes affected by PEX than normal eyes. Moreover, it is confirmed that there is impairment of the blood aqueous barrier in the eyes of those affected with PEX at the level of the ciliary body [9]. Lens metabolism depends on the aqueous. Alterations in the iris vasculature and blood aqueous barrier could affect the composition of aqueous and subsequently could affect the lens metabolism, resulting in cataract formation.

PEX is a risk factor for open-angle glaucoma. Glaucoma may confound the association between PEX and cataract. Moreover, the nuclear cataract surgery with PEX was successful after adjusting for open-angle glaucoma. This suggests that PEX may contribute to the development of cataract through a pathway different from that responsible for elevated intraocular pressure or open-angle glaucoma [10].

PEX causes zonal fragility, leading to a higher risk of dropped lens. In addition, eyes with PEX dilate poorly, making surgery technically difficult. As a

result, eyes with PEX have a higher rate of operative complications such as capsular rapture, zonular dehiscence, and vitreous loss. PEX had been shown to increase the incidence of posterior capsular opacification after cataract surgery [11]. It is also observed that PEX may also increase the incidence of cataract and cataract surgery.

Summary and Conclusion

As the cataract surgery in pseudo exfoliation is challenging. The proper evaluation intra-operative complications and modified surgical technique will lead to successful cataract surgery with PEX.

The present study demands such clinical trials must be carried out in a large number of patients at hi-tech hospitals where the latest techniques are available to combat any surgical emergencies because exact pathophysiology pseudo exfoliation is still unclear.

Limitation of study: Owing to tertiary location of research centre, small number of patients and lack of latest techniques, we have limited finding and results.

This research work was approved by Ethical committee of Government Medical College Nandurbar Maharashtra-425412

References

1. Shafiq I, Sharif-ul-Hasan K: Prevalence of pseudo exfoliation syndrome in a given population Pak. J. ophthalm. 2004, 20; 49-52.
2. Tayler HR: Pseudo exfoliation syndrome is an environmental disease. Trans ophthalmol. Soc. UK 1979, 99; 302-7.
3. Duke Elder S: Disease of the Lense and Vitreous, vol. XI, St. Lows. The CV mosby and company 1969, 47-57.
4. Brooks Anv, Gillies WE: The presentation and prognosis of glaucoma in pseudo exfoliation of lense capsule ophthalmology 1988, 95; 271-6.
5. Baig MA, Niazi MK: Pseudo exfoliation syndrome and secondary cataract Pak. Armed Forces Med. J. 2004, 54; 63-66.
6. Carpel EF: Papillary dilatation in eyes with pseudo exfoliation syndrome Am. J. ophthal. 1988, 105; 692-4.
7. Arvind H, Raju P: Pseudo exfoliation in south India Br. J. ophthal 2003, 87; 1321-3.
8. Ring vold A, Davanger M: Iris neurovascular in eyes with pseudo exfoliation syndrome. R. J. ophthal. 1981. 65 (2); 138-41.
9. Kuchle M, Viores SA, Mahlow J: Blood aqueous barrier in pseudo exfoliation syndrome evaluation by immune histochemied albumin. Grafes Arch clin. Exp ophthal. 1996, 234 (1); 12-18.
10. Kanthan GL, Wang JJ: Use of anti-hypertensive medications and topical beta-blockers and the long-term incidence of cataract and cataract surgery Br. J. ophthal. 2009, 93 (9); 1210-1214.
11. Ritch R, Schlotzer Schrehardt U: Exfoliation syndrome surv. Ophthalmol. 2001, 45 (4); 265-315.